

CIP

COWAM In Practice

European-level Guidelines

for the Inclusive Governance of
Radioactive Waste Management

Ensure that local
communities are not simply
'affected' but are influential
and sustainable

Create policies and structures
that facilitate cooperation
among stakeholders

Create means to develop,
test and carry out improved
governance processes

European-level Guidelines for the Inclusive Governance of Radioactive Waste Management

CIP (Community Waste Management In Practice) is a research action gathering a wide spectrum of stakeholders from five European countries, interested in **how society should manage the radioactive wastes** that result from nuclear power production and/or from medical, military or industrial applications.

CIP set up a process allowing each national group to identify issues important for the good governance of radioactive waste management (**RWM**) in their own context, and to conduct cooperative research into these issues. CIP considered not only 'greenfield' siting of new waste management installations, but also **how stakeholders can contribute to improving all aspects of RWM, now and over the long term.**

These Guidelines represent the principal messages and ideas from CIP delivered to Europe-27.

The CIP process – and these Guidelines – are meant to help prepare the way for more **inclusive governance** of RWM in Europe.

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What do we mean by **inclusive governance**?

Processes that engage the widest possible variety of players in decision making around common affairs.

In the field of radioactive waste management there are many "best practice" publications. What distinguishes CIP EU-level Guidelines from other recommendations is the setting in which this guidance has been developed. In each of the five participating countries – **France, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, UK** – CIP provided a framework for a diversity of stakeholders to cooperate, on an equal footing, in identifying and investigating what they saw as important issues in RWM governance. This cooperative research process itself was a way to prepare more inclusive governance.

Inclusive governance

- Recognizes that no one player or organization has the resources, knowledge, and/or authority necessary to tackle common affairs alone.
- Seeks to foster interaction among the different networks of players in preparing decisions that will be well-founded, transparent, fair, sustainable and effective.
- Implies that action can be taken at appropriate levels, in a manner complementary to the power or the formal authority of the State.
- Recognizes that all citizens, with or without mandate, are entitled to take an interest in public issues and to address them.

The CIP Guidelines focus on societal and technical issues highlighted by the diversity of participants in their own specific contexts – with special consideration for the local level.

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Context

Civil society and institutional players have both complained about a ‘democratic deficit’ in radioactive waste management (**RWM**). The deficit results from certain characteristics of traditional decision making:

- A focus on decisions prepared exclusively by experts and public servants.
- A strict reliance on representative democracy.

Traditional decision-making frameworks tend to assign a passive role to civil society. They assume that ‘experts know best’, and that the public interest is best defended by the State and by representatives acting ‘for’ the population.

However, there are several strong motivations to seek change and to create processes of decision with (rather than ‘for’) members of society, and to let civil society contribute actively to RWM:

- The UNECE Aarhus Convention recognizes that wider participation can foster better, more sustainable decisions. The Convention establishes citizens’ right to obtain information, their right to participation, and their right to seek justice.
- The quality and safety of RWM over the long term depend not only on technical arrangements, but also on civil society’s vigilance and follow-up. Citizens have vital contributions to make at every phase: developing knowledge and expertise, shaping decisions, and monitoring the performance of waste management installations during operation and after closure.

In the past decade or more, there have been great efforts in many European states to develop citizen participation in environmental decision making and particularly in RWM. Despite progress, however, dissatisfaction is still found.

Institutional arrangements for involving civil society typically aim at informing the public or at gathering input at designated times. These actions are not designed to transform traditional decision-making frameworks. Instead, traditional information and consultation are meant to reinforce these frameworks’ efficiency and – as has been repeatedly seen in the history of RWM - to help overcome crises when decisions are contested or when decision-makers lose credibility or legitimacy. The main objectives of these traditional ‘involvement’ arrangements are to make decisions more acceptable, and to reassure civil society that an adequate job is done by mandated decision-makers. There is little notion that citizen participation might continue past those goals, and that citizen participation actually forms a vital requirement for the quality of RWM over time.

Citizen participation is a right

Safe management depends also on citizen involvement

Typical institutional arrangements for ‘involving’ the public do not resolve the democratic deficit because they do not address the root causes of the deficit

To eliminate the democratic deficit, transform traditional decision-making mechanisms

The democratic deficit in RWM is not addressed by delivering more acceptable decisions. The democratic deficit is eliminated when the governance of RWM becomes a democratic activity. The deficit can only be diminished properly when the broad range of societal players is empowered to make a meaningful contribution.

There are real challenges in organizing broadly inclusive participation:

- How to ensure balance, independence and quality?
- How to respect legislative structures and the 'silent majority'?
- How to design articulations between established decision-making structures and civil society?
- How to set a common agenda?
- How to negotiate a shared framing of the issues?
- How to combine technical expertise and societal aspirations into a working management solution?
- Which formats can allow direct participation in decision making, and which formats will best help the range of stakeholders prepare and review decisions?
- What support will citizen players need in order to participate?

While these challenges are great, they need to be addressed in the case of RWM, because safety over the long term will be improved when civil society can play an active role.

The change-seeking process engaged in CIP is one response to the challenge of transforming RWM governance

The CIP project took place from 2007 to 2009. It is part of COWAM (Community Waste Management), a ten-year participative European reflection on RWM governance. The **themes** investigated in CIP are presented on pages 6-7.

CIP proposes **Guidelines** on constructing inclusive governance in the radioactive waste management area. These guidelines, and criteria for assessing governance situations, are presented on pages 8-21. Three **pillars** are seen to support inclusive RWM governance, detailed on page 22.

The Guidelines emerge from the work of stakeholder participants in France, Romania, Spain, Slovenia and the United Kingdom. CIP also set up and tested **tools and methods of cooperative research**, whose specific goal was to help prepare the transition to more inclusive governance in RWM. The CIP framework and experience are described on pages 23-28.

The lessons learned from the CIP process offer potential inspiration for other European players who wish to support a transformation towards more inclusive RWM governance in their own context. **Conclusions** – perhaps applicable as well in other complex socio-technical areas – are presented on pages 29-31.

Inclusive governance is aided by legal texts like the Aarhus Convention. Inclusive governance relies too on the emergence of autonomous categories of civil society players, with the means to build their competence and influence in the processes of collective action

CIP Themes of Investigation

Find research briefs associated with each theme at www.cowam.com/CIP.html

- *Contribution of Local Communities to RWM Safety*
- *Participatory Assessment of Decision-Making Process*
- *The Local Partnership Approach to the Siting of a RWM Facility*
- *Local Liaison Committees and their National Association: French Experience*

- *Long-term Environmental Surveillance and Health Risk Assessment*
- *Practical Governance of Reversibility*

- *Defining an Affected Community*
- *Sustainable Territorial Development Associated with Radioactive Waste Installations*
- *Community Support/Involvement Packages*

Across the 5 CIP countries, participants identified **3 major themes** they wished to investigate:

Structuring local communities and **developing local democracy** for engagement in radioactive waste management governance

CIP participants wanted to learn how local communities (alone or linked – from villages to regions, as appropriate) can get organized to play a stronger role in RWM decision making. The CIP Guidelines spell out five vital features that support communities' ability to engage.

Sustainable long-term governance of radioactive waste management

Local stakeholders are concerned about how to sustain vigilance and responsibility for RWM facilities over the phases of their development and operation, and throughout the many years beyond. The CIP Guidelines give details on passing along a 'safety legacy'.

Affected communities and sustainable territorial development encompassing radioactive waste management

Administrative borders are not enough to define the communities affected or concerned by the existence of any RWM project. The CIP Guidelines point out ways for an inclusive governance process to accommodate different definitions of community, and to provide resources for engagement and development.

These were three avenues leading to issues of interest to all the participating stakeholders – even if they had differing views or positions.

CIP participants in the 5 countries undertook cooperative investigation on their chosen governance themes. This research effort in itself allowed the stakeholders (national, regional and local representatives of civil society or the State, as well as technical specialists) to test out an inclusive governance approach. They practiced a new style of relations, reframing RWM issues to address the stakes, concerns, perspectives and goals of the different player categories.

Examples of CIP topics:

In **France**, the cooperative research allowed an exchange of views and knowledge on implementing reversibility, identifying major issues on which players then expressed their expectations.

In **Romania**, strides were made in empowering local stakeholders to participate in decision making, now and in the long term. The group looked at roles for local players in vigilance over nuclear and waste installations and their potential health and environmental impacts.

In **Spain**, stakeholders examined the economic development that should accompany the siting of a storage facility. Materials were developed to support mayors in talking with their community about technical and social concerns.

In **Slovenia**, where local siting partnerships exist, evaluating and developing the role of citizens in RWM decision making was at the heart of investigations.

In the **United Kingdom**, addressing the complex question of ‘defining an affected community’ was highly pertinent in the current stage of the national siting process, and provided an opportunity for stakeholders to dialogue across borders.

Learn more about the specific background to CIP cooperative investigations, the findings and the learning process in each National Stakeholder Group, by consulting the Prospective Case Studies at www.cowam.com/CIP.html

Detailed CIP Guidelines for each theme, and criteria for assessing actual governance situations, are found in the following pages

Constructing Inclusive Governance of RWM: European-level Guidelines and Criteria

In all 5 countries, CIP cooperative research brought together stakeholders from many horizons.

A special focus was given to local players' needs and concerns.

The outcomes of the CIP discussions of each theme are reflected in the Guidelines on the following pages.

Supporting the engagement of local communities in RWM decision-making processes is justified by law and by ethics. Moreover, local players and communities can play a strong, useful role in RWM governance. They can facilitate and contribute to:

- The development and assessment of any proposal to site and build a RWM facility in their territorial context.
- The quality of follow-up at every stage of the facility life cycle.
- The continuity of this long-term follow-up through inter-generational vigilance.

In these ways, local communities and players are **an important resource** for assuring the protection of health, well-being and the environment – in their own territory, and for the nation.

Developing Local Democracy

Guidelines for constructing inclusive governance *and Criteria for assessing governance situations*

Traditional decision-making approaches...

- ✦ See national, elected representatives as having most legitimacy to shape national processes

- ✓ Consider that local, regional and national stakeholders each have legitimate interests and input

- ✦ Set agreements with local authorities before involving the public

- ✓ Help the full range of players come together to generate agreements

- ✦ Organize public information with the goal of improving acceptance

- ✓ Organize public involvement with the goal of improving decisions

- ✦ Consider that local players should just say 'yes' (or in the worst case, 'no')

- ✓ Empower stakeholders, particularly local players, to make meaningful decisions and influence other decision-makers at each successive phase in facility siting, operation and beyond

- ✦ Consider that local stakeholders are concerned for just a limited period of time (the siting phase)

- ✓ Consider that local stakeholders are a vital resource for vigilance and for safety over the generations

- ✦ Set short reply deadlines

- ✓ Adapt deadlines so that local players have time to develop competent input

- ✦ Call on technocratic expertise to counsel high-level decision-makers

- ✓ Ensure legal status and material resources for local competence building

- ✦ Consider that localities should be dealt with separately

- ✓ Foster national and European networking, federation and pooling of experience and resources among concerned local players

- ✦ Consult, without integrating what is learned

- ✓ Take due account in decision making of local and regional input, as per the Aarhus Convention

Inclusive governance approaches...

CIP investigations about "Developing Local Democracy" emphasized that communities' ability to engage fruitfully in RWM governance depends on at least five elements

a. Capacity to assess whether it is justified and desirable to site a RWM facility in a particular territorial context

'Is it acceptable to site a RWM facility here?' This is not a simple question, and if the answer is 'yes', it will engage the community across several generations. Local players and communities should be empowered to assess whether it's justified and desirable to host a facility. The reply does not concern only technical features, nor does it depend solely on risks and benefits. Local stakeholders will also need to consider ethical and practical aspects. Their job is facilitated by:

- Voluntary entry into the siting process, with the right to voluntary withdrawal or veto.
- Arrangements for study, debates and deliberation within the community.
- Phased decision making, allowing communities to check and refine the siting justification with new information at each step.

b. Arrangements for multi-level governance: how national, regional, and local decision processes fit together, and the possibility for local players to influence other levels

How 'local' is 'local democracy'? The participation of local stakeholders in RWM decision making does not take place in a vacuum. The local level is inevitably impacted by the decisions taken at other governance levels.

Integrating with issues, players and forums (formal and informal) at the other governance levels (region, State) is therefore a key condition for local engagement to be meaningful and sustainable.

Multi-level governance is facilitated when the decision-making process is designed to include:

- A clear stepwise decision-making process identifying phases, milestones, roles for different levels of decision, and rules for assessing readiness to go to the next step.
- An institution tasked with helping the process move forward while guarding quality.
- Mechanisms for involving the different levels and balancing their input.
- Mechanisms for ratifying and validating decisions, including broad-based democratic expression.
- The right and opportunity for local players to express common concerns at upper decision levels, and to influence the relevant decisions.
- A pragmatic plan for local engagement (legal frameworks give the minimum opportunities that should be available, but RWM is likely to require a higher level).
- Support for the engagement of local communities (e.g. through financial engagement packages).
- Legal and financial means to develop adapted local structures (e.g. Local Committees) that will help organize local participatory democracy.
- Classical routes of communication provided by representative democracy (Mayors, Members of Parliament ...) but also interaction between the local participatory process and the regional and national decision making processes.
- The ability to find recourse if decisions are taken unfairly.
- Regular independent assessment of processes.

Communities with strong leadership, good deliberation processes, and procedures for developing a long-term sustainable development vision are more successful in influencing decisions. National and European networking of communities also proves to be an efficient and useful tool.

Beyond the specific provisions of national RWM policy, a variety of national, European and international legal or regulatory provisions support the engagement of local communities in RWM governance :

- National legal frameworks for environmental decisions.
- EU Directives on Environmental Impact Assessment and Strategic Environmental Assessment Engagement.
- The Aarhus Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters.
- Directive 2003/35/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 May 2003 providing for public participation in respect of the drawing up of certain plans and programmes relating to the environment and amending with regard to public participation and access to justice.

Because RWM policy overall can have an environmental impact, the engagement of local communities in RWM decision making should be encouraged and supported - not only for siting decisions but at all RWM policy stages.

C. Quality of local democracy: how the diverse local players work together to address RWM issues

Meaningful participation in RWM decision making represents a considerable effort. It requires local players and communities to mobilize themselves and to sustain their mobilization over time (in particular after the siting decision) with sufficient intensity. The quality of local dialogue and debates is also paramount.

A key challenge for higher governance levels is to support local democracy while safeguarding the autonomy of the local community in the process.

To make their full contribution to RWM, local communities need at least:

- Sufficient time and means for carrying out local dialogue.
- A safeguarded independent role in the decision-making process.
- The ability and capacity to organize themselves in a way that suits their particular context.
- Arrangements to allow good, influential links between participatory democracy and elected representatives.
- Proper engagement and open lines of communication with upper governance levels.

The quality of local dialogue or debates should not be considered on procedural grounds only (diversity of engaged players, transparency of debates, clarity of the rules governing the debates ...). It should also be considered with a view to its outcomes at the local level:

- How do local debates contribute to the development of a shared understanding of local RWM arrangements integrating all dimensions at stake (risks, local development, inter-generational perspective ...)?
- How do local debates influence the decisions of the elected representatives?

d. Development of the necessary skills and know-how for follow-up

Addressing RWM issues requires a local community to mobilize and develop expertise inside and outside the community. This is a time and resource consuming process for a local community.

It may be facilitated by:

- Dialogue processes to help build up local players' skills and competence.
- Opening up expertise – choosing issues to investigate, engaging own experts, stretching institutional experts.
- Availability of a diversity of external expert resources to support the investigations carried out by the community and foster the development of local skills and expertise.
- Means for upkeep of local skills and know-how across the years.
- Assuring transparency and traceability.
- Networking and pooling resources with other local communities, nationally and internationally.

e. Integration of RWM activities into a broader sustainable development project for the territory

In addition to the monitoring and safety mechanisms implemented by the waste managers and by national public authorities, local communities may wish to exert autonomous vigilance over a RWM facility with potential impacts on health and the environment, thus bringing an additional contribution to safety.

Local vigilance is easier for local players if RWM activities are not carried out in isolation but are integrated in the socio-economic life of the community and are part of an overall development strategy for the community. Key conditions for this are :

- A careful design of the benefits associated with the RWM facility according to the characteristics of the various affected communities, in order to reinforce the sustainability of the affected communities.
- Local dialogue and assessment on the development project associated with the RWM facility (including consideration of alternative sustainable development projects).
- Facilitation of sustainable cooperation between the various affected communities and between the engaged local players.

Being involved in the governance of site operations and in facility monitoring will help the local community and players to develop:

- Know-how and expertise on radioactive waste issues.
- A robust and sustainable memory of the site.

Example

The engagement of French Local Liaison Committees (CLI) and their National Association (ANCLI) in French RWM issues

Local actors federate

In 2006, the ANCLI organized 4 meetings with several French CLI to produce a White Paper on RWM governance, as a contribution to the national public debate that helped in preparing the new French Planning Act on RWM.

Encouraged by this cooperative exercise, in September 2006 several CLI attached to nuclear facilities joined with the CLIS of Bure (the Local Information and Oversight Committee attached to the Bure underground research laboratory) to form a permanent ANCLI working group on radioactive waste and materials.

This working group pools local resources and expertise to investigate key radioactive waste and materials management issues (e.g. practical reversibility of a deep geological disposal; tritium discharges) from the point of view of concerned local communities, be they hosts to waste-producing or to waste-managing activities.

The ANCLI contributes to the national debate on RWM by issuing opinions grounded on the outcomes of these investigations.

From the CIP research brief: *Local Liaison Committee and National Association of Local Liaison Committees: French Experience*

Sustainable Long-Term Governance of Radioactive Waste Management

Guidelines for constructing inclusive governance
and Criteria for assessing governance situations

Traditional decision-making approaches...

- ✘ Lock up future decision making with successive irreversible decisions

✔ Involve players in agreeing on criteria for going forward or backing up in a stepwise process

- ✘ Over-emphasize the need to take responsibility now

✔ Preserve the capacity of future generations to influence decision making on RWM

- ✘ Over-rely on passive safety

✔ Engage civil society's vigilance as a potential long-term contribution to the safety of RWM

- ✘ Over-rely on passive long-term memory mechanisms

✔ Foster the communities' role in keeping knowledge and concern alive

- ✘ Reserve monitoring to professional expertise

✔ Meet communities' expectations to play a role in long-term vigilance and to work out the corresponding arrangements

Inclusive governance approaches...

A safety legacy

There is no single definition of 'the long term'.

From the technical point of view, operators and safety authorities must assess the 'long-term' performance of protection systems over periods of time ranging from several thousand to a million years. What does such a 'long term' mean to society?

The current generation is concerned with and can cope best with the near future. A reasonable approach is for the current generation to create governance processes fostering the continuous transmission of a safety legacy to the next generation(s) in order to ensure the continuity of waste management.

The safety legacy should equip the next generation (and onwards in turn) to sustain **vigilance**:

- ✓ Monitoring physical radiological levels and facility performance.
- ✓ Surveillance of potential impacts from the facility upon health and environment.
- ✓ Making, implementing and reviewing decisions when necessary.

Passing on the legacy is a question of inclusive governance over time. Developing and carrying forward the safety legacy requires the continuing involvement of the various categories of players (authorities, experts, citizens, local elected people, associations...) at several different levels (local, national, international).

CIP participants investigated two main aspects of long-term inclusive governance in RWM:

- Involving local stakeholders in long-term vigilance regarding environmental monitoring and health risk assessment.
- Implementing the concept of 'reversibility' for deep geological disposal in a practical way.

These cooperative investigations included a review of experiences, and delivered insight on the practical actions necessary to implement long-term vigilance.

Our generation has to invent ways to pass on a safety legacy composed of:

- ✓ Knowledge
- ✓ Know-how
- ✓ Safety procedures
- ✓ Protection options
- ✓ Institutions
- ✓ Resources
 - Lasting financial provisions
 - Sustainable socio-economic development of host territories

Supporting long-term vigilance

The facility operator, under the control of the national safety authority, is responsible for implementing a monitoring system for a radioactive waste facility. However, involving civil society and other players at different governance levels (local/national/EU and international) should improve both capacity and sustainability of vigilance.

The **development of citizen vigilance** is a key element for improving the sustainability of vigilance over the long term. The development of citizen vigilance is achieved through the **involvement of local players in the overall surveillance system** in order to:

- Address their questions and concerns at the planning stage and find a mutual understanding of the issues at stake.
- Identify potential improvements of the monitoring system and management of the radioactive waste installations.
- Build citizen confidence in the ‘institutional’ monitoring system.
- Work out the specific contributions that citizen vigilance can make, identify the practical aspects of implementation, and build up local structures to play this role.

Citizen vigilance in practice should cover the following main aspects:

- The waste inventory.
- The integrity of the disposal system (waste packages, installation...) over time.
- The implementation of the ‘reversibility concept’.
- The potential environmental impacts.
- The potential health impacts.

Maintaining vigilance over the long-term also implies the ability to **set up a system to ensure intergenerational transfer of knowledge** in order to preserve professional and citizen expertise and organizational control over the radioactive waste facilities.

Another issue associated with long-term vigilance is that of **keeping alive the memory of the installation** and ensuring its transfer through future generations. In this field, it is necessary to make a distinction between ‘passive’ and ‘active memory’ which are both important:

- Passive memory is made up of all the archived documents that can be used to track the history of the disposal facility, its design and contents, the results of environmental monitoring, etc. The durability of passive memory relies mainly on information redundancy and on the location of the archives.
- Active memory means that knowledge of the facility is brought to the attention of the public over the course of successive generations. To keep the memory alive it is important to sustain economic and social life in the vicinity of the waste facility. To this end, the task of monitoring the facility should be integrated into a general sustainable social and economic development plan for the area.

Example

The opinion of local players in Meuse/Haute-Marne, France

Sustaining economic and social life

In France, local players around the Bure laboratory express concern about maintaining a stable local and regional demography. The areas surrounding the laboratory are not densely populated, and the populations are consistently decreasing and ageing. Sustainable social and economic development plans therefore need to be implemented, in order to encourage young people to remain in these areas over the generations.

From the CIP research brief:
Practical governance of reversibility

Inclusive governance across the whole RWM facility lifetime: From siting to post-closure surveillance, including design and operation

According to the stage of development and operation of the RWM installation, different levels of local stakeholder involvement can be envisaged in order to ensure a continuous vigilance over the facility. This involvement has thus to be planned at the time of deciding on:

- The site of the radioactive waste installation.
- The conditions of reversibility (agreeing the criteria that will trigger decisions to terminate or to extend the period of reversibility, to retrieve waste, to seal the disposal facility...).

➤ The practical aspects of operating and monitoring the disposal system. For example, if safety standards evolve over the lifetime of the facility, the feasibility of updating the facility must be reviewed. From the outset, a role in the future reviews should be instituted for the local stakeholders.

In the pre-operating or early operational stages, the local stakeholders should participate also in defining meaningful indicators to be used within the monitoring system, for example:

- Selection of indicators to follow up the evolution of the disposal facility (evolution of waste packages, feasibility of removing the waste...).
- Establishment of reference levels to permit the estimation of environmental or health impacts.

The follow-up of these indicators, defined through consultation, would aim at progressively improving confidence in the assumptions used in the safety analysis, and reviewing the assumptions when necessary.

Finally, stakeholders should be involved in the follow-up of financial aspects associated with operation, maintenance or monitoring of the disposal facility.

Example

French High Commission for Transparency and Information on Nuclear Safety (HCTISN)

Circulating the results of monitoring

'HCTISN recommends that the operators of closed radioactive waste storage sites should regularly present to the Local Liaison Committee:

- ✓ the inventory of all substances stored at the site,
- ✓ the results of monitoring their impact on the environment,
- ✓ the measures taken to reduce their impact,
- ✓ and the relevant schedules.

Also, discussions should be held between the stakeholders on site issues.'

From the CIP research brief: *Practical governance of reversibility*

Example

Inclusive governance of RWM according to CIP in France

Addressing long-term issues

- ✓ Set up vigilance systems for RWM facilities that give a significant role to local players in an intergenerational perspective.
- ✓ Ensure local players' independent access to pertinent expertise for their concerns on vigilance, facility monitoring and follow-up of territorial impacts.
- ✓ Provide for citizen and technical partners to cooperate in investigating the technical, but also ethical, political, legal, financial and societal dimensions of the practical implementation of reversibility and retrievability.
- ✓ Develop citizen inspection and control of the transfer of radioactive materials and wastes on to the facility site.
- ✓ Organize active memory features based on intergenerational transmission of a safety legacy.
- ✓ Institute administrative and financial arrangements to guarantee that it will be possible to reverse actions or to retrieve waste, according to agreed criteria.
- ✓ Work out governance arrangements that fulfil the Aarhus Convention rights of local players to access information, participate in decision making, and have legal recourse, all along the planning process and throughout the facility life cycle.

Affected Communities and Sustainable Territorial Development

Guidelines for constructing inclusive governance
and Criteria for assessing governance situations

Traditional decision-making approaches...

- ✘ Focus on ‘acceptance for a potential RWM facility’

- ✔ Place the emphasis on ‘building a sustainable territorial development plan including a justified RWM component’

- ✘ Drive forward with a main objective of meeting deadlines

- ✔ Help local communities to engage by offering stepwise and reversible decision-making processes

- ✘ Focus on siting in economically disadvantaged territories with ‘nothing to lose’

- ✔ Provide the time and resources needed for territories to examine and evaluate democratically a potential candidacy or hosting project, and to look deeply into the whole set of issues that may be raised

- ✘ Place cash payments at the centre of community decisions about hosting a facility

- ✔ Help local territories to work out a diversified and coherent long-term development plan compatible with RWM facility hosting

- ✘ Result in competition and rivalry between local entities

- ✔ Stimulate synergy, cooperation between communities, and grouping into partnerships around a long-term territorial development plan

- ✘ Progressively result in a situation of financial dependency for candidate communities

- ✔ Separate the **engagement** package (support for the democratic study of how to fit RWM into a territorial plan) and the **benefit** package (investments in economic and cultural development in the project host territory)

Inclusive governance approaches...

Who and what are affected communities?

What is the extent of the community affected by a RWM project? How may the concept of community be used to focus upon sustainable territorial development? How should 'community' be defined to help take appropriate decisions about benefits packages?

Geographic features (and underlying geological characteristics), infrastructure and other physical features may be useful in outlining the communities concerned. Administrative borders will play a role. However, it is especially important to respect the ways in which people define their own communities, and to grasp in this manner what precisely may be 'affected' by a project. Such a meaningful definition may rely on at least four key elements of the experience or 'sense' of community:

- ✓ Membership
Identity and the sense of belonging.
- ✓ Emotion
Attachment to a home place, the feelings and symbols of community.
- ✓ Integration
Local democratic processes that mobilize people.
- ✓ Reinforcement
Economic activities and networks that knit together a 'functional' area.

Each of these elements may have a different spatial extent. For example, individuals' feeling of membership and their emotional sense of place may be associated with a small geographic area, its typical landscape and tight-linked relations among people. At the same time, their elected representatives may govern a larger political district. The daily activities and networks that reinforce community may be spread over still another functional economic area that includes several towns, for instance, or links them with a city. Finally, economic development is seldom a purely local affair and its institutions may superimpose another area on the map. Although they are local initiatives, sustainable development plans often involve wider territorial players in private, public and social sectors.

In the case of a RWM facility, a 'directly affected population' may be embedded in a larger, multi-dimensional set of communities, all of which experience some impact from the siting process and from the subsequent phases of facility development, operation, and long-term monitoring.

An inclusive governance process will be broad-reaching, recognising the need to accommodate these different levels and perspectives of community.

You don't need to be 'directly affected' to be interested, involved, and potentially valuable to the process. Not only elected people or professionals have a legitimate stake in RWM projects.

Four inter-related themes may be important when thinking about affected communities and their engagement in a RWM siting process:

Framing

There is no single ‘right’ way to look at fitting a RWM project into a local territorial plan. Distinctive and even competing perspectives will be found among members of the various communities who have a role to play. Some stakeholders may want to tightly restrict the discussion. Others will bring in many issues and levels of concern. One step in inclusive governance is to bring the variety of perspectives or ‘frames’ to light. A good process will be able to accommodate different frames or ways of talking and thinking about RWM and its governance.

Flexibility

Governance processes should be able to accommodate the different spatial scales of the elements of a community experience and the gradual emergence of a ‘directly affected population’. A good process will:

- ✓ Accommodate adjustments in community definition as the siting process becomes territorially narrower and more specific.
- ✓ Acknowledge that the term ‘community’ may conceal great diversity.

Fit

Facility siting processes will be more effective if they take into account the fit between the community experience of ‘directly affected population’ members and wider cultural, economic and political elements. A good facility siting process will:

- ✓ Recognise the relationships between directly affected populations and those wider communities of which they are also members.
- ✓ Appreciate that such relations support the sustainability of communities and of projects.

Finalisation

The sustainability of the economic community within which the directly affected population is embedded will need to be supported through a benefits package. The closure of a facility siting process is not the end of the radioactive waste governance process and across the years, an operating facility will need to be a good neighbour to both a directly affected population and to wider economic interests. Sustainable territorial development takes a long-term perspective and requires a long-term solution.

Example

Affected communities according to CIP in the United Kingdom **A practical approach**

Policy on siting a geological disposal facility in the UK recognizes three levels of ‘community’: Host Community, Wider Local Interests, and Decision Making Body. Including these three levels in the facility siting process is intended to retain flexibility to account for local circumstances. The UK participants in CIP decided to focus on how the communities can be defined in practice. A practical proposal would be:

- ✓ Firstly, find out who feels affected. The residents around a potential siting candidate area can be surveyed to find out who considers that the proposed RWM facility will have an impact on their lives, and in which ways.
- ✓ Then, survey and interview individuals in that population about the various groups and networks they belong to in different parts of their lives. Where do people work or go to school, where do they spend time with family and friends, where do their other activities take place? Where do they call ‘home’? Where do they care about? Where are they engaged in community life?
- ✓ Then, map the different communities these individuals belong to. Tracing the spatial reach of individuals’ various communities will help to assess how wide a territory is actually affected by a potential RWM facility. This will provide an understanding of the functioning socio-economic area that is touched by the candidate installation. It will be a goal to foster this area’s sustainability.

From the CIP research brief: *Defining an Affected Community*

Benefit packages and sustainable development for affected communities

Benefits packages and their role in sustainable territorial development focus much attention in facility siting processes. It is commonplace for RWM facility siting processes to include rules for constructing the packages that could be granted to affected communities, and also to include discussion about and negotiation of such packages.

The scope and scale of benefits packages may be closely related to the definition of 'affected community'. Benefits packages can be designed to sustain the economic community within which the directly affected population is located. Outsiders' perceptions of the community or territory could also be taken into account in plans to enhance sustainable economic development, especially if a negative perception or stigma should result in economic loss.

Successful processes tend not to impose benefits packages, but rather to design them in negotiation with a locality. The application of rigid legal instruments to designate the scope, scale and purpose of benefits packages can be problematic: they offer little margin for negotiation or adaptation to specific local needs and requirements, and can result in gross inequalities between components of the directly affected populations.

In contrast to applying rigid criteria for benefits based on spatially or administratively defined zones, a governance process based on identifying a directly affected population, and the diversity of communities in which it is embedded, offers welcome flexibility.

Rigidly constructed reference compensation packages may polarize communities. Experience from some countries illustrates potential problems: discussion has centred on the amount of money to be transferred to a single administrative territorial unit, rather than on working out sustainable development plans for the full extent of the affected community. Dialogue has turned into bargaining between central and local/regional government, leaving aside civil society. Conflict may grow between neighbouring units when they find themselves in competition for a single, sometimes very large sum, and frustration may harm formerly good relations within and between communities.

Review of European practice in the application of community benefits demonstrates that other, less divisive schemes have been devised and implemented, in some cases leading to improved community coherence. For example, an alternative strategy has been adopted in Sweden where two municipalities studied for several years the issues raised by a facility siting project. Because the designated siting community will get direct and spin-off benefits from hosting a repository, this community will receive a smaller proportion of the overall benefits package compared to the community that was not chosen to host the facility. In this way both communities feel that if they have gained from the process.

Example

The UK 'Managing Radioactive Waste Safely' policy for geological disposal

Supporting communities in two different aspects of their participation in RWM governance

- An engagement package enables communities which express an interest in hosting a facility to participate in the selection process, in particular through a Siting Partnership.
- A benefit package marks recognition that a community which hosts a geological disposal facility for radioactive wastes will be volunteering an essential service over time to the nation.

This distinction was felt very useful to overcome a situation where communities feel that compensation creates obligations, without their having the resources and the opportunity to discuss their short- and long-term role.

Example

Benefit packages according to CIP in Slovenia and in the United Kingdom

A cooperative analysis

Two of the five CIP countries examined community reactions and impacts associated with the various types of potential benefits. Their review of European experience highlighted a few factors to be borne in mind when designing a benefits package to accompany affected communities during siting and beyond:

- ✓ Allow full community involvement in designing an integrated project to fit into a territorial development plan; no two communities are identical and each will have differing aspirations.
- ✓ Work through local partnerships involving and representing all parts of the directly affected population; foresee the articulation with wider local interests and community decision-making bodies.
- ✓ Build local capacity to allow full understanding of the benefits proposals and ensure that community competence-building activities are funded to the full extent necessary.
- ✓ State clearly how benefits will be allocated, using legal agreements if necessary.
- ✓ Seek government (or implementer) action to ensure that benefits negotiated for coming years will be protected from future changes in legislation or policy.
- ✓ Incorporate transparent fund management processes.
- ✓ Include trans-generational benefits to support long-term community involvement.
- ✓ Foster the development of local businesses and workforce whenever possible.
- ✓ Encourage involvement of local youth through training and support schemes.
- ✓ Incorporate property value protection schemes - these also indicate confidence that impacts will be low.

PILLARS of Inclusive Governance

Key findings from across the cooperative investigations in the 5 CIP countries suggest that inclusive governance of RWM stands on 3 pillars:

Ensure that local communities are not simply 'affected' but are influential and sustainable

- Ensure a recognized role in the legislated decision process for local and regional leaders and local citizens.
- Guarantee the means to develop their voice, and that this voice is heard and taken into account.
- Design a mutually beneficial territorial development project encompassing RWM.
- Target quality of life and socio-economic development of local/regional contexts now and in the long term.
- Develop the communities' effective role in following up the management of wastes.

Create policies and structures that facilitate cooperation among stakeholders

- Create opportunities and provide means for the diversity of stakeholders to frame jointly the issues and undertake action.
- Enable stakeholders to develop an integrated understanding of issues that are neither purely technical nor purely societal.
- Verify that administrative rules or boundaries do not exclude those who have a contribution to make.
- Ensure effective links of communication and influence between the different levels of decision making and the different communities involved.
- Sustain relations among stakeholders across time, to enable continued response to management challenges as they arise.
- Provide flexibility so that policy can adapt to new events and understanding.

Create means to develop, test and carry out improved governance processes

- Create specific working groups or purpose-built, temporary frameworks.
- Build a democratic culture of problem framing and problem solving.
- Support the emergence from civil society of new, autonomous RWM players with skills and resources to play a permanent role of vigilance.
- Connect with established decision-making processes to bring to them the benefits of inclusiveness.

So that a diversity of players with different perspectives, stakes, tasks, and concerns can build a new system of relations and improve the quality of RWM now and for the future

The CIP Process

COWAM History & Background

CIP built upon **COWAM** – a European network (2000-2003) that reflected on how to improve governance from the viewpoint of local and regional communities concerned by RWM, and **COWAM 2** – a research action (2004-2006) bringing together stakeholders from 14 countries to investigate more deeply the themes uncovered by COWAM.

CIP – COWAM in Practice – then set up a practical process (2007-2009) to allow a diversity of stakeholders in 5 separate countries to frame RWM issues, pinpoint pertinent questions and develop knowledge and recommendations in a cooperative manner, drawing on and reinforcing European experience.

- The story of each group's cooperative research is presented in a CIP Prospective Case Study.
- The data and results of the cooperative investigations are written in Research Briefs and their Executive Summaries.
- The major insights emerging from these five country groups and their investigations are presented here in European-level Guidelines.

Learn about all three COWAM programmes and find their documents - guidance, reports and summaries - online at: www.cowam.com

CIP was supported by the European Commission and by various national sponsors in 5 participating countries - **France, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, UK** - that are at different stages in setting up RWM management solutions.

CIP's objectives:

- Enable progress in the inclusive governance of radioactive waste management (RWM).
- Follow up and analyze national processes of RWM governance in the five European countries.
- Support stakeholders, particularly local communities, directly in their engagement with the issues of RWM.
- Capture the learning from that experience for the EU-27, in the form of online reports and these European-level Guidelines.

Different stakeholders have different ethical positions, values and pragmatic views regarding the sources of radioactive wastes, and regarding the best means to manage them over time.

Some stakeholders or countries stated firm conditions for their participation in the COWAM programmes. By common agreement, COWAM investigations and discussion focussed on the management of only the existing waste inventory, and did not endorse any specific management solution.

COWAM in Practice: Going National and Local

Community Waste Management and COWAM 2 framed RWM governance at a European level, organizing a series of EU-wide seminars and conferences, each time involving about 200 delegates. A broad diversity of stakeholders, of different profiles and representing a dozen countries, met on an equal footing to investigate key RWM governance issues: local democracy, the links between local communities and national policies, quality of decision-making processes, and long-term vigilance. Thus the first two COWAM projects benchmarked good practice and generated recommendations for the EU, building on concrete feedback from a wide range of countries and RWM processes. These good practices and recommendations were adopted in several countries to help improve the governance of RWM.

In countries that had recently become European Member States, participation in COWAM activities proved very useful to allow the main stakeholders to meet with their European counterparts, and just as importantly, to establish connections between national institutions and local communities. Local NGOs and Mayors, representatives of agencies and other specialists from a single country sometimes met for the first time at a COWAM meeting. As a neutral European stage COWAM made intra-national networking easier, for both new and traditional Member States. In COWAM 2, intra-national discussions were tested during annual conferences. Grouped by country, participants debated the lessons they found most pertinent for their own context. These country-based multi-stakeholder groups found an interest in elaborating the issues together. For a number of countries in particular, this discussion format appeared promising.

COWAM in Practice, the third programme to be organized, recognized that achieving good practice in a given country doesn't derive merely from learning what was done well or badly elsewhere. Once good practices are identified - supported by evidence from a broad variety of local and national experiences across Europe - improving actual governance requires experimentation in a dialogue between stakeholders in their own environment.

Stepping into experimentation seemed possible in several countries at the end of COWAM 2. What made it "the right time" in each of these places? The conditions were quite diverse. In some countries, like France or the UK, a new legal or policy framework had just been promulgated, and stakeholders were keen to discuss how the new regulations could be set into motion and what the practical implications could be for local communities. In Romania, the limited development of RWM legislation called for joint work between the variety of stakeholders to develop the basis for democratic local governance of nuclear and RWM issues. In Spain and Slovenia, despite well-established relations between national and local stakeholders there was a need to assess existing RWM governance arrangements and to consider how these could be improved. In all these various contexts, the existence of a temporary European/national institution like COWAM in Practice was deemed useful to develop an insightful dialogue on RWM governance.

The CIP Framework for Cooperative Research

*CIP has been an experiment in cooperative research – a suggested process for preparing or engaging in inclusive governance of RWM.
How did it work?*

The diversity of CIP participants in five European States took part in a structured framework that left them free to develop their questions about RWM and to cooperate in finding answers.

- *The elements of this framework – groups, roles, and activities, resources and tools – are described here.*
- *The main features and principles of CIP are defined as well.*

Groups, Roles and Activities

National Stakeholder Groups

A diversified group of stakeholders with concern and interest for RWM (reflecting their context and their position), they request specialist input, actively elaborate that input, test the cooperative process, make proposals for improving inclusive governance of RWM, build skills and relationships and share knowledge. These groups met in their own country 5 times over the course of the 3-year project.

National Facilitators

Players capable of bringing the stakeholders together in each country, they recruit a diversity of participants, organize the meetings around the themes chosen by participants, provide a link to the European project.

National Stakeholder Group Chairs

Players with a mandate of representation at the local level or representing a federation of local communities at national level, they bring the local communities into view, and collaborate with the National Facilitator to ensure that pertinent themes are identified and addressed.

Methodological Task Force

Specialists from a range of disciplines, at the service of the National Stakeholder Groups, they respond to the groups' interests by proposing concepts, information, and tools, and reflect the cooperative research in the written Research Briefs.

Core Group

The meeting of National Facilitators and Methodological Task Force members, they develop insight into the national and European governance lessons learned throughout the cooperative research process.

Steering Committee

The meeting of National Facilitators, National Stakeholder Group Chairs, project managers and representatives of an Operator, a Regulator and a National Research Institute, they conduct a yearly review of the project activities, strengthen the fit between research efforts and stakeholders' concerns in the five countries involved, and ensure that stakeholder views are properly taken into account in written products.

Resources and Tools

Memorandum of Agreement

– a document signed by each participating body, in which the aims of CIP, the rules and negotiated conditions of participation were specified.

Success Criteria, Reflexive Interviews

– these tools furnished the means to assess the CIP process.

- The Steering Committee proposed Success Criteria that participants used to evaluate each national meeting.
- In-depth interviews were conducted in the 5 countries with a total of 25 participants representing different stakeholder roles. Their reflection on the CIP project is summarized on the next page ('What CIP Achieved').

Research tools, methodologies

– Among the knowledge resources provided for the cooperative research by National Stakeholder Groups were:

- international case studies, from the literature or from CIP fact-finding actions;
- roundtables to gather participants' views and statements;
- territorial seminars to extend the cooperative research to a wider number of stakeholders;
- group investigation exercises like 'SWOT' (analyzing Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats).

Features and Principles of the CIP process

Opening a door to change

To approach more inclusive democratic governance, specific processes of cooperation are needed. CIP is a temporary process parallel to the actual governance system. It creates specific conditions allowing a new system of relationships to emerge among the concerned players.

Inclusiveness

CIP participants take a step back from their usual governance context with its strict role divisions, to reflect on RWM issues together. The CIP process brings together stakeholder categories who may not meet otherwise, to cooperate in investigations that may cut across their habitual or mandated areas of action.

Power sharing

While it is not a place for decision making, the National Stakeholder Group meeting is an arena for confronting and developing ideas. Usual hierarchies (experts or decision makers vs. citizens) are put aside in this arena where each player's contribution potentially has the same value. This pushes each participant to better define the interest, position and knowledge of his or her stakeholder network, and each participant can assess the position of others.

Reframing

Defining 'what are the important questions to ask' is the shared task of CIP participants in their national group. Taking a new perspective on the issues currently structuring the RWM governance process is facilitated by processes allowing specialists and various concerned players to look into issues in a cooperative manner, without necessarily abandoning their specific positions or values. The Methodological Task Force members offer resources (methods, case studies, experience) these players can use to start developing answers, to reshape their understanding, and to uncover further questions together. Sets of players may undertake their own autonomous investigations before interacting with other categories of players.

Democratic culture of cooperation

Going beyond a simple discussion of ideas, the CIP framework helps participants to build up shared skills aiming at improving governance. The experience allows people to test how governance of RWM could be enhanced by applying such rules of democracy and cooperation, sharing power and knowledge-building.

Reflexivity

Players are invited not only to participate in a structured cooperative research process, but also to think about their experience there, and its links or gaps with the RWM governance system they are part of. They may seek to translate the cooperative processes and outcomes of CIP into the actual RWM governance structures in order to make these more inclusive.

Sustainability

The system of relations set up and experienced during the defined term of CIP, as well as the research insights, can be used and developed by stakeholders after CIP, for ongoing governance of RWM.

What CIP achieved

The CIP experience and its impacts were analyzed in interviews granted by 25 persons representing the full range of stakeholders. They pointed out what was achieved in CIP, their gains or disappointments. Overall, they expressed their willingness to continue developing inclusive governance practices.

Political Impacts

Opening a door to change

Interviewees say that through the cooperative research activities, CIP enabled most participants to develop their democratic culture: more familiarity with the rules of the RWM game, better handling of multi-stakeholder discussions, increased ability to listen to the others, better understanding of the complexity of problems, etc. Through these discussions, new systems of relations between players were built up.

The categories of stakeholders most affected by CIP were typically the local players around the sites, and sometimes players from the national agencies or authorities. They were able to form new contacts and alliances, as well as improved technical understanding.

The local players who saw the most change or impact were those who started in a weak position and could hence, thanks to CIP, find themselves in a stronger position. CIP gave the opportunity to some civil society players to participate even though their country's current governance framework foresees no official role for them, or a severely limited role. In the CIP process, they could voice their concerns and expectations and share their perspective on RWM in their country. Civil society players were active in bringing alternative viewpoints and proposals to the table. They formed or reinforced working relations with the other stakeholders. In this way CIP contributed to the emergence and empowerment of some civil society players (citizens, associations).

In some cases the balance of power was changed. Certain stakeholders found their relative influence reduced, but for a broad range of other players the CIP process allowed increased influence.

CIP was considered as an adequate arena to discuss topics, not to negotiate. Thus, CIP discussions could address 'how', rather than 'when' or 'with whom' a specific RWM process should be undertaken. It was seen that CIP could contribute to improving the methodology used in decision-making processes.

Sometimes citizens or associations were reluctant to intervene in the discussion of complex issues, and took rather a position of listener or observer. A small minority chose to withdraw from the process, when disappointed by the lack of direct access to national decision making or to decision-makers. In each stakeholder category, there were players who chose not to join the CIP process or who minimized their participation at various times.

During CIP most participants took part in informal processes of negotiation that were parallel to CIP, since CIP was not structured as a decision or negotiation forum. The experience gained in CIP led some stakeholders to shift or refine their strategic position, as they became more aware of the actual governance situation and of the resources they could use or rely on.

Re-framing RWM Issues

CIP discussions allowed RWM issues to be placed in a larger context of opportunities for local autonomy and development, beyond the restricted logic of compensation (although in some contexts the issue of compensation remained high on the agenda for certain participants).

CIP helped to develop practical insight into some complex issues, such as: the formal administrative and technical plans for RWM; the definition of 'affected communities'; possibilities for setting up citizen committees or citizen vigilance; pragmatic aspects of reversibility; financial schemes within national RWM programmes, etc.

During CIP discussions, some players (including the national agencies or authorities involved in CIP) took into account issues introduced by others. Still CIP did not always result in a shared understanding of identified problems (divergent interpretations persisted in several contexts).

CIP offered an opportunity to evaluate existing governance practices, and allowed National Stakeholder Group members to identify together factors that block or impede the establishment of a decision-making process that is satisfactory for all stakeholders. In at least one context, the CIP process furnished a model for handling a different management issue (e.g. in Spain, for water resource management).

Overall evaluation

The feeling about CIP at the end of the project is predominantly positive, but mixed: the players who are satisfied are those who were able to gain a better understanding of the opportunities of their situation; the players who are dissatisfied are those who saw their position of power recede, or those who could not influence the empowered decision-makers as much as they would have liked. At the end of CIP, a majority of the participants are willing in one way or another to continue cooperative research and more inclusive governance processes in their country.

Participating in CIP enabled most stakeholders to form insight into the processes, methods and tools of inclusive governance, especially because they developed a clearer vision of the RWM situation. CIP is identified, especially by the less experienced players, as a place for shared learning (regarded as something different from learning in isolation). The Methodological Task Force (the specialists tasked with bringing European case studies and background information) played a useful role mainly for the local players, but also for some institutional players who improved their understanding of the themes chosen by their group.

In general the participants agreed that the project was adequate to raise awareness and foster better understanding among different stakeholders on a variety of complex issues. They agreed that the CIP project set a precedent for relevant stakeholders in the radioactive waste management arena to gather and discuss issues regarding specific siting processes or RWM issues in general.

CIP is a temporary institutional process that offers a discussion forum less formal than some others. It enables the development of a different system of relations among the players. CIP was perceived mainly as a process to test and prepare an inclusive governance approach. It was felt to be helpful in creating the conditions for fruitful discussions and by sustaining the players through cooperative research. Even those who consider that their country situation remains blocked, feel that the shared learning and development of democratic culture in CIP are clear gains to support future governance practices. On the whole, the participants in CIP are willing to continue this type of cooperative research endeavour.

Conclusions from the CIP Process

Radioactive waste management is a complex social and technical process. Experience, expectations, and legislative trends all point to developing new forms of governance for RWM. What can COWAM in Practice teach about moving from traditional management arrangements towards more inclusive democratic governance?

CIP, a cooperative research process led in five countries, is a three-year experiment aimed at developing democratic culture in the context of RWM. The CIP process was based on:

- Multi-stakeholder cooperation, with specialist support.
- Reframing RWM issues.
- Working out new strategic positions (especially by local players).
- Self-reflection on frameworks and processes to foster joint action.

CIP supported the exploration of a new system of relations among stakeholders in an area that is often polarised by conflict. In France, Romania, Slovenia, Spain and the UK, a diversity of stakeholder participants came together, with the assistance of European specialists, to bring many perspectives to bear on the complex issues of RWM.

CIP members came together to reflect on how to improve RWM governance arrangements in their country: their joint work in itself was testing and helping to create the conditions for change towards inclusive governance.

CIP is a bounded, three-year programme which nonetheless had meaningful interactions with the ongoing, multi-year RWM governance process in each country:

- The members of the National Stakeholder Groups, each with a separate role – or lacking a role – in the ongoing process, had a place to network and dialogue.
- They investigated topics of central importance in their current RWM context, and their findings could be brought to bear in the ongoing process.

The CIP process was designed to support participants in reframing RWM to include the values and the issues brought up by new categories of stakeholders.

The emergence of these new categories of players may prompt an evolution in actual governance. From their new strategic position they may make contributions in the democratic forum (beyond the limited consultation appointments granted by traditional processes). Such an empowerment of autonomous local civil society players is accompanied by a shift in the political status of RWM, which progressively takes on the status of a ‘public affair’. It is no longer the sole affair of public authorities and operators.

In conclusion, this type of framework bringing together a variety of players (citizens, associations, committees, elected authorities, public authorities, specialists, etc.) proposes a type of constructive democracy (rather than simply representative, nor even participative or deliberative). With a temporary experimental set-up, it attempts to create the conditions for inclusive governance and ongoing cooperation among the stakeholders. In this way, constructive democracy aims to foster the autonomy of civil society as a full-fledged player on an equal footing with the State or other institutions whose role is to organize and support citizen participation.

Potential contributions of multi-stakeholder cooperative investigation to improved governance

Cooperative investigation in a wide-ranging group of stakeholders can facilitate:

- Reframing issues and stakes into a shared vision.
- Drafting meaningful policies and projects.
- Developing hand-in-hand the technical and societal aspects of RWM.
- Integrating the diversity of contributions to strengthen projects or solutions.

Another key element: Champions

The CIP participants acknowledge the role of the individuals who support the development of democratic culture in each of the five countries. Their personal conviction, persuasive energy, and courage are helping other people and institutions to change.

Specific added value

CIP National Stakeholder Groups were not mandated to take decisions. They demonstrated the value of a neutral meeting ground, enjoying connections with other, more strategic contexts, in order to:

- Build stakeholder relations.
- Reframe RWM as a public affair incorporating multiple values and perspectives.
- Produce knowledge, investigation results and experience.

Each of these contributions can serve decision making.

How to benefit directly from the CIP cooperative research findings?

- Call the diverse stakeholders together in your context to discuss the themes investigated (Developing Local Democracy, Sustainable Long-term Governance, Affected Communities).
- Talk about whether you encounter the same issues in your context.
 - Do you have all the elements that CIP participants suggest are vital?
 - Are they working correctly?
- Collect ideas for how these elements could be reinforced in your context.
- Have discussions about how to implement these ideas.
- Identify questions and issues that need further investigation in your context.

Diagram

Actions to help open the way to inclusive governance

A temporary process in the perspective of durable change

This diagram shows how a cooperative research process (like CIP) may help move towards a more inclusive mode of governance in the countries where it is applied.

The cooperative research process is limited in time. It is embedded in the larger, actual RWM governance process that started before and will continue afterwards.

The process helps to level out the differences in power, knowledge and resources that are commonly found among players interested in RWM governance. The organizers (stakeholder group facilitators) and task force of specialists offer tools to support learning.

Participants try out a democratic system of relations while they identify and investigate issues of common concern. They frame the issues in a way that takes into account the values of the various players – including ‘new’ players from civil society and local communities. These players can gain a strategic position that may allow them to continue to make their voice heard after the investigation process is over.

Looking back over the cooperative process in a ‘self-reflective’ analysis helps participants to identify the methods and rules that they want to translate into ongoing governance procedures. The understanding gained through the entire process can help to transform the permanent features of local, national or European governance.

Overall, the cooperative research process looks to transform RWM governance durably by reinforcing the players’ democratic culture, by offering new, inclusive issue framings, and by fostering the empowerment of new categories of players from civil society.

À vous de jouer ! Alegerea vă aparține! i Depende de vosotros ! Odvisno je od vas! It's up to you!

COWAM in Practice set up a process of cooperative research into Radioactive Waste Management (RWM) in five countries: France, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, the UK.

The CIP process:

- ✓ Offered empowerment to local communities as vital stakeholders in RWM;
- ✓ Facilitated dialogue among local and institutional stakeholders in a setting unpressured by their ordinary duties;
- ✓ Deepened national insight through drawing on and contributing to European and international experience.

In the five "National Stakeholder Groups" organized by CIP, stakeholders

- ✓ Identified themes of importance for their RWM context;
- ✓ Investigated the themes through discussing case studies and background information provided by specialists.

The study material has been written up into nine research briefs, organized around three main themes. Themes and findings are explained in this document.

These European-level Guidelines for improving inclusive RWM governance were developed on this basis. They have been reviewed and validated by the leaders of CIP from the 5 countries.

This document presents
insights and guidance for improving governance
that emerged from the five groups' thematic findings developed through
the **CIP framework for cooperative research.**

It also looks at **what was achieved** by such an experience.

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See the complete list of partners at

www.cowam.com/CIP.html